

MAKING THE IELTS MORE COMMUNICATIVE, MOTIVATIVE AND MEANINGFUL TO EFL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Internationalisation is of growing significance worldwide, with obvious changes and broader developments in higher education around the world. In order to fulfill the requirements of institutions and universities worldwide, IELTS exam has become essential for EFL learners who want to study abroad in an English speaking nation. Offering access to higher education in developed parts of the world, IELTS preparation courses could be strongly influenced by the principles of communicative language teaching (Green, 2007). As an instructor, the responsibility is not only raising the awareness of exam strategies but also to enhance the needed skills which may bring the learners success in later life. The purpose of “exam preparation” might be considered too narrow and controlled in comparison with modern TESOL principles which aim at maximizing authentic communicative contexts and student-centred activities. Rather than just an introduction of the exam format and “teaching the test”, modern world encourages teachers take into account the achievement of more stimulating ways of ensuring a healthy balance between social and academic language acquisition. Hopefully, this speech could bring a reflection on to what extent IELTS classes could become more communicative, motivative and meaningful to learners, and then propose several classroom activities, focus on how to teach the test in a communicative fashion.

Keywords: IELTS teaching, communicative, meaningful, student-centred.

1 INTRODUCTION

The IELTS tests English skills that students will continue to use long after the exam; therefore, IELTS teachers are of dual-purpose role in the classroom. Not only do they need to prepare students for the exam itself, but also teach them a new language, which means conveying knowledge in a communicative and engaging environment. As a result, IELTS class should be a relaxed environment in which students involve actively to think and use language on their own, by interacting with one another through communicative activities. However, most of IELTS candidates emphasized a higher score on the exams rather than a true enhancement of their language proficiency. They are often seriously focused on the test and their time span for preparation course is short, so implementing a whole communicative approach has become a challenge for teachers. In this case, a flexible use of various communicative techniques in an IELTS lesson plan would be a possible solution. This article aims at introducing several examples in designing communicative, interactive activities while connecting students to specific parts of the test.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section aims at discussing the key concepts of communicative language teaching (CLT) and P-P-P model to see how teachers can connect features of the IELTS test with effective language learning process.

Communicative language teaching

The term 'Communicative' has long been used as a methodology of teacher's choice. Hymes' (1972) theory is considered as a core philosophy of what constitutes 'communicative competence'. In accepting this concept, educators believe that it involves both knowledge of the language, and the capacity for using this in context. Widdowson (1978) argued that language courses should concentrate on the 'use' of language rather than the 'usage'. He defined 'usage' as "That aspect of language which makes evident the extent to which the user demonstrates his knowledge of linguistic rules" and 'use' as, "That which makes evident the extent to which the language user demonstrates his ability to use his knowledge of linguistic rules for effective communication" (p.3).

According to Littlewood (2000), "A communicative approach opens up a wider perspective on language. In particular, it makes us consider language not only in terms of its structures (grammar and vocabulary), but also in terms of the communicative functions that it performs" (p. x).

Although there have been different theories, one area in which educators do agree is that in CLT, learners should spend as much time as possible to use appropriate language forms to successfully express real-life messages. Communicative language teaching can be realized as a set of principles and goals of language teaching, including the choice of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom.

CLT Activities and Techniques in Test Preparation Classes

In applying CLT principles in practice, new techniques and activities are required for developing new roles for teachers and learners. These kinds of activities allow learners to use the target language to negotiate meaning via interaction with teachers and friends. Stryker and Leaver (1997) stated that "learning a second language has been compared to learning to ride a bicycle, learning to play tennis, or learning to play a musical instrument" (p. 3). By saying this, they appreciate the importance of practice in language learning process. According to Larsen-Freeman (2000), "Students use the language a great deal through communicative activities such as games, role-plays, and problem-solving tasks" (p. 129). Therefore, educators can adopt certain communicative activities to encourage learners to produce English while acquiring necessary strategies.

The IELTS preparation course

The IELTS exam is a standardized test, aiming at measuring candidates' language proficiency.

In previous studies of the IELTS Writing elements, the significance of social factors has been identified, as they impact on interpretation of prompts (Mickan, Slater and Gibson 2000), and on the structure of candidate responses (Mickan and Slater 2003). In another study, the complexity of the process of constructing and the need to analyse the social purposes of communicative tasks was emphasised (Mickan 2003). Likewise, studies of oral testing module have examined social factors which impact on performance, in particular, in the way the contexts and purposes of oral tests affect learners' achievement (Yu and Mickan 2005).

These studies suggest that candidates' performance on tests are influenced by their classroom discourse experiences. Therefore, during IELTS preparation course, it is important that learners are provided with knowledge of elements of the test, test-taking strategies as well as how to enhance their language ability. It is the teacher that should provide his students with opportunities to negotiate ideas about the test contents, whereas working as a facilitator promoting classroom interaction. In this case, activities adopted from communicative language teaching theories would fit learners' needs.

3 SUGGESTED ACTIVITIES

Instructing students to a high IELTS band score can be a long process including the mastery of various techniques and dealing with the various question types, and time management strategy. For this reason, communicative techniques can be used to design a lesson plan with activities that help students achieve those targets while upgrading their language proficiency. In this section of the article, the activities reflecting certain elements of Communicative Approach together with P-P-P model will be introduced as effective tools for IELTS preparation course.

IELTS writing task 1 and practice stage activity

A dictation run

In practice stage, students have chance to expose to the provided structures and get used to the formation of language by repetition. This activity gives students chance to learn language through actions and drill. In pairs, the students must create a chart from a model report of IELTS writing task 1 containing the target vocabulary. This model report is stuck to the wall on one side of the room. One student runs to the report, reads it, and then dictates the details of the report according to his memory, and his partner need to create a chart based on the dictation.

The challenge is inverted when the first drill is finished, another chart is provided and the students must create the summary themselves based on the knowledge they receive from the model. After completing both drills, students will acquire knowledge related to graphic description while practicing speaking, listening, writing and reading skills in an interactive classroom environment.

IELTS listening and practice stage activity

Synonyms jump

This activity takes place after the simulated listening test is done and the students finish checking their result. In this stage, students need more chance to expose to word formation or paraphrasing of phrases. Teacher divides class into two big groups. Two representatives from each group go to the board, standing face to face. On the floor, in front of their feet are the circles (or printed footprints) to jump onto. Students are assigned with list of phrases that appeared from the listening test and listen carefully from the test recording to recognise words or phrases that mean the same as the words in the list, e.g. "unhappy" - "unsatisfied". The person recognises the word first will quickly jump onto the footprint. This is great practice for the IELTS test when the words in the question and the audio file are not the same.

IELTS reading and practice stage activity

Read and run

Most of the time, reading is considered as a solitary activity and while-reading stage triggers the image of individual work instead of a collaborative activity. Running and reading activity allows learners to apply scanning strategy while approaching to language in a race.

The class should be divided into two groups A and B. Group of student A sit at one end of the classroom while the text to be read is on the wall at the other end of the room. All students in A group are given a list of questions. They then read the questions to B students who have to run down the classroom to find the answers in the text, and then run back to dictate the answers to student A, who then write the answers onto the given paper. The first pair to answer all the questions wins.

IELTS reading and production stage activity

Summarised speech

After finishing the reading test, students can be given a speaking task in which they use key language from the text to produce a speech while practicing summarising skill. Teacher may provide students with a list of key phrases from the reading passage. In group of four, students use the provided words to summarise what they have read in their own style, speaking English to the others. The other group members use structures of expressing opinion to state their agreement on the content of the summary e.g. “I totally agree with you” and so on. This activity gives students opportunity to consolidate their knowledge while interacting with their peers.

IELTS writing task 1 and production stage activity

The survey

In the production stage, the students must produce the target language more freely. In this activity, students produce their own chart and the IELTS-style summary of the chart while taking part in speaking activity. Firstly, teacher provides pairs of students with survey questions (e.g. “What is your favourite sport?”) and have them collect answers from the others. They then use the collected data to create their own chart which can be pie or bar chart. After finishing, they will write a summary of their results using the target language or present their charts to another pair of students to summarize.

IELTS reading and production stage activity

Peer Discussion

After doing an IELTS reading test, students work in groups or pairs to compare their results, using the provided sets of language to protect their idea and convince their partner (e.g. “I choose A because I think that...”, “I could not agree with you more”) When students get the agreement with one answer, they move on to the next question. This activity allows students to speak out key words from the reading text while thinking of the strategy to choose the correct answer, and convincing their partner.

IELTS writing task 2 and pre-writing stage

Debates

This is a great way to generate ideas on different writing topics. It’s important that teacher choose the topic carefully, something that students can relate to, something they will be interested in and

want to talk about, such as a ban of using mobile phones in school campus. More importantly, they should be made very similar to IELTS essay questions.

Teachers should make sure that students are provided with scaffolding language for expressing opinions, for agreeing and disagreeing and for supporting ideas with examples or explanations before doing the debates. Besides, the scale of the debate is also important, it can be in class or in smaller groups. In order for the debating process to happen smoothly, there should be a person who control the debate, and some people who judge who wins. The people involved in the debate need to have enough time to practice what they want to say. The teacher can assign some students in the audience a helpful task like looking at the verbal and non-verbal language of their friends.

4 RECCOMENDATION

Managing mixed-ability classes

It is very common that there are students with widely differing abilities for specific skills in IELTS classrooms, which can be challenging for teachers. The teacher then, need to be flexible in grouping students so that they can support and learn from one another. Moreover, understanding students' various targets for the IELTS band score would also be helpful to give them suitable motivation and strategies.

More importantly, in choosing and designing the activities for IELTS class, teacher can adapt the activities to fit learners' level of language proficiency such as giving extra task for high-level students.

Developing a positive and collaborative working atmosphere is one of the key strategies for managing mixed level classes. Moreover, teacher should assign a variety of task suitable for different levels such as giving weaker students homework to consolidate classroom knowledge, while providing stronger students tasks that are a bit more challenging than classroom requirement to maximize their ability of using language.

As most of the possible solutions to the problem depend on cooperation between the members of the class, it is essential to capitalize the chance for teamwork and for the class to use English wherever possible in classroom communication.

An integration of four skills

An effective English course in general and IELTS preparation course in specific should involve a mix of all four skills – reading, listening, writing, and speaking. Those skills should be blended together to some extent. This is considered as an effective method to develop students' communicative competence given that classroom activities allow them to acquire the language from receptive skills while producing language through productive skills. In a listening class, mix with a little speaking; with a writing class, blend a little reading as well.

5 CONCLUSION

In short, The IELTS can seem overwhelming at first to both teachers and students. That's why advanced preparation is absolutely the key. IELTS preparation classes can be more interesting, motivating to learners by implementing communicative activities into suitable stages of classroom practice. By conducting various learner-centered activities relevant to the test content, the IELTS preparation process would be more meaningful to learners. It is crucial for language teachers to

keep in mind that the activities should draw students' interest as well as their background knowledge. The effectiveness of the students' test preparation will increase when the students are excited and actively involved in the class activities.

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